

DISCO₂ STORE

POZZOLANIC ACTIVITY QUANTIFICATION OF HOLLOW GLASS MICROSPHERES

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ABSTRACT

Hollow glass microspheres (HGMS) have been widely used in the hydrocarbon industry for cementing wells with low-density slurries. These consist of amorphous siliceous hollow spheres filled with gas, providing a low-density material with high strength. The present study aims to characterize the interaction between HGMS and the cement paste, focusing mainly on the development of the pozzolanic activity, given the nature of amorphous silica. Therefore, two HGMS of different crush strength levels were studied. HGMS were used as a replacement of total cementitious binder at 10% by weight of cement. The pozzolanic activity was measured within the modified Chappelle test, the portlandite quantification from thermogravimetric analysis, and the strength activity index. Additionally, isothermal calorimetry analysis, X-ray diffraction patterns and scanning electron microscopy images were obtained. Results demonstrated that HGMS interact with the cement paste initially as nucleation agents and later with a pozzolanic reaction, presenting an activity comparable to that of metakaolin or fly ash.

Keywords: Hollow glass microspheres, pozzolanic activity, lightweight cement, oilwell cement

INTRODUCTION

In order to obtain lightweight cement slurries, different low-density materials have been used for cementing extraction wells. Within this application, hollow glass microspheres (HGMS) are very popular and are widely used [1]. HGMS are lightweight, high-strength materials manufactured from soda-lime borosilicate glass. These consist of hollow glass spherical bubbles with a determined wall thickness that provides them with high crush strength, in terms of which they are classified. Their glass wall is mainly composed of SiO₂ (60% - 87%) [2]. They are produced with a particle size varying between 20 and 70 μm, densities from 100 to 800 kg/m³, and crush strength up to 186 MPa (27000 psi). Such properties make them very suitable for their application in extraction wells.

The first reported field application of HGMS in the hydrocarbon industry dated from 1980 [3] when it was intended to overcome the low-pressure gradient of an offshore wellbore in the Gulf of Mexico. Two cementing jobs were accomplished using a cement slurry with HGMS. A low-density cement slurry (1115 kg/m³) with better mechanical properties than the lightweight cement slurries previously used was achieved. Following this first and successful field application, HGMS have been studied to comprehend their behaviour under the conditions present in oil wells. These studies are mainly centred on the properties obtained on cement slurries with different classes and percentages of HGMS. Some of these researches are presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Using HGMS in oil well cement slurries, relevant aspects of analysed researches

Research	HGMS Density	HGMS Crush Strength	Admixture proportion	Slurry density	Compressive strength
	[kg/m ³]	[MPa]	[HGMS mass ratio % bwoc]	[kg/m ³]	[MPa]
[4]	Not specified	Not specified	0.00	1740	33.3
			3.00	1620	17.9
			12.00	1560	19.2
			18.00	1500	22.0
			20.00	1500	17.3
[5]	Not specified	Not specified	18.00	1320	9.7
[6]	380	27.6	10.43	1460	11.4
			12.41	1400	9.5
			14.82	1340	6.4
			17.67	1280	5.3
	420	55.2	11.86	1450	10.4
			14.16	1390	9.2

			16.92	1330	6.8		
			20.19	1260	5.1		
			460	131.0	13.31	1460	9.1
					16.02	1400	7.0
					19.15	1340	5.7
					22.98	1280	4.2
600	41.4	19.28	1460	8.1			
[8]	200	3.5	5.16	1550	21.0		
			6.84	1470	20.0		
			8.58	1330	10.7		
	250	5	6.45	1500	22.3		
			8.55	1480	20.7		
			10.73	1310	12.3		
	320	14	8.26	1530	27.3		
			10.94	1410	17.7		
			13.73	1280	11.7		
	400	28	10.32	1540	28.0		
			13.68	1430	27.0		
			17.16	1390	31.0		
	600	55	15.48	1550	36.5		
			20.52	1500	38.0		
25.74			1480	26.0			
[10]	250	5	0	2050	46.0		
			4.27	1770	41.0		
			6.45	1720	32.0		
	400	28	0	2050	46.0		
			6.84	1770	45.0		
			10.32	1720	35.0		
	600	82	0	2050	46.0		
			10.26	1880	49.0		
			15.48	1720	44.0		
[11]	Not specified	Not specified	0.00	1815	17.9		
			10.00	1265	6.5		
			30.00	950	3.4		
			50.00	850	2.1		
[32]	250	0.8	0.00	2280	55.1		
			7.10	2240	57.5		
			14.50	1980	46.4		
			22.10	1740	30.9		
			29.30	1590	21.5		
	320	2.0	0.00	2310	51.3		
			6.87	2240	52.0		
			13.92	2070	46.9		
			21.51	1900	44.8		
			28.82	1660	35.1		
	380	5.5	0.00	2300	46.0		
			6.71	2220	46.9		
			13.69	2060	52.7		
			21.30	1870	48.4		
			28.59	1660	35.2		
	500	10.0	0.00	2300	50.1		

			5.61	2170	55.0
			11.65	2130	59.1
			18.14	1940	57.5
			24.73	1770	50.9
	600	10.0	0.00	2300	48.7
			7.07	2210	55.5
			14.60	2090	61.2
			22.09	1900	52.2
			29.20	1700	48.5

Mavares and Pertuz [4] and Abdullah et al. [5] attempted to design slurries for cementing wells that go through formations with low fracture gradients. Both fulfilled the requirements involved in this application with the addition of HGMS in proportions ranging from 12% to 20% by weight of cement (bwoc). They designed slurries with densities between 1730 kg/m³ and 1500 kg/m³ and compressive strength ranging from 33 MPa to 17 MPa. The most widespread lightweight well slurries, which are obtained by increasing w/c ratio, were demonstrated inappropriate because of their high density and low compressive strength.

Mata and Calubayan [6] analyzed the relationship between density, cement replacement percentage, HGMS crush strength (or class), and compressive strength of cement slurries. They kept constant the w/c ratio, and four target densities were fixed: 1260 kg/m³, 1320 kg/m³, 1380 kg/m³, and 1440 kg/m³. These densities were achieved by replacing cement with HGMS in different percentages. In **Table 1**, it can be observed that the strength of the slurries for different targeted densities varies with the class of HGMS. This variation can be explained given that different classes of HGMS also have different densities. It is interesting to notice from **Table 1** that the class of HGMS with the highest crush strength is not the one that yields the highest compressive strength for a targeted density of a cement slurry. Nevertheless, there is a relationship between HGMS' density and slurry's compressive strength. This indicates that the lower the HGMS' density, the lesser the amount needed in the slurry to lighten the density, therefore, the higher its compressive strength.

HGMS were also studied as addition for engineered cementitious composites [7–10]. Composites were designed with fly ash, silica fume, polyvinyl alcohol fibres and HGMS. Fly ash was replaced by different classes of HGMS from which a decrease in density ranging from 300 to 700 kg/m³ was obtained. It was concluded that increasing the dosage of HGMS implies decreasing the compressive strength of the resulting light-weight composite. Furthermore, for identical vol. % of fly ash replacements, the light-weight composite with the HGMS of higher crush strength yielded the higher compressive strength. Additionally, coated HGMS were used as fly ash replacement [7]. Within SEM and EDS analysis a chemical and physical interaction between coated HGMS and cement hydration products was observed.

Nevertheless, this interaction is yet to be deeply studied. Given that HGMS consist of amorphous silica, pozzolanic activity between this admixture and the cement paste is expected [11]. Pozzolanic materials react with calcium hydroxide (CH) present in the cement paste to form calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H), which strengthens and increases the durability of cement pastes. The reactivity of these materials relies on their chemical/mineralogical composition, fineness, the w/c ratio, and the proportion used.

Lanzón Torres and García-Ruiz [12] studied the pozzolanic activity of hollow micro-spheres and expanded glass, both of which have similar chemical composition to HGMS used in the present study. Compressive strength and conductivity measurements in hydrated lime suspension and cement suspension tests were carried out in designed specimens with the addition of the mentioned materials. These authors concluded that both supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) presented some pozzolanic activity, mainly because of the results obtained in the compressive strength test. Moreover, the conductivity measurements developed under both conditions (hydrated lime and cement suspensions) endorsed this behaviour.

The present work aims at providing clarification on the pozzolanic activity of HGMS by multiple quantifications through a variety of traditional and novel methods. Some authors have indicated that HGMS or very similar materials present pozzolanic activity, but not concluding experiences have been carried out to confirm this behaviour yet. Therefore, two different classes of HGMS were tested in a designed well cement slurry. The experimental program includes isothermal calorimetry, thermogravimetry analysis (TGA), modified Chapelle test, powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) and the determination of the strength activity index (SAI).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials and mixture proportions

Cement slurries used in this research work consisted of class G moderate sulphate-resistant portland cement [13] provided by Petroquímica Comodoro Rivadavia (Argentina), HGMS27 and HGMS41 (3M) (**Figure 1**), polycarbonate-based superplasticizer (ADVA 570, GCP Applied Technologies) and deionized water. **Table 2** shows the oxide composition, and **Figure 2** shows the particle size distribution of class G cement and both classes of HGMS. Class G cement has a density of 3110 kg/m³. HGMS27 has a crush strength of 27 MPa, a density of 280 kg/m³, and mean particle size (D50) of 30 µm, while HGMS41 has a crush strength of 41 MPa, a density of 460 kg/m³, and a D50 of 40 µm.

Figure 1: Scanning Electron Microscopy 1600x images of (a) HGMS27 and (b) HGMS41

Table 2: Oxide composition of class G cement, HGMS41, and HGMS27.

Element	Class G cement	HGMS41	HGMS27
SiO ₂	19.30	60.30	60.90
CaO	52.20	11.40	11.00
Na ₂ O	0.53	6.37	5.98
Br ₂ O	1.74	0.84	0.90
P ₂ O ₅	0.14	0.57	0.56
SO ₃	2.09	0.27	0.29
Al ₂ O ₃	3.30	0.08	0.14
MgO	3.27	0.08	0.10
Fe ₂ O ₃	18.20	0.04	0.05

Constant water to solid ratio (w/s) of 0.44 was used in all slurries as specified by the American Petroleum Institute for class G cement slurries [13]. The superplasticizer presents a solid residue by oven drying of 33.9% mass percent according to ASTM C 494 [14]. It was added to the slurries with HGMS to obtain constant fluidity equal to that of a cement slurry without HGMS (CS00). Its proportion was set at 0.3% and 0.2% liquid weight bwoc for cement slurries with HGMS27, and HGMS41, respectively. The addition of 10% bwoc of HGMS was made as partial replacement of cement. Final mixtures proportions are shown in **Table 3**. Given the properties of HGMS, a decrease in the slurry density is expected when they are added. In fact, fresh slurry CS00 had a density of 1890 kg/m³ while fresh slurries CS41 and CS27 developed a density of 1530 kg/m³ and 1280 kg/m³, respectively. This means that, by the replacement of cement with 10% bwoc of HGMS41 and HGMS27, a 19% and 33% decrease in density was obtained. It can be appreciated that the density obtained for fresh slurry CS27 is lower than that of CS41, which is related to the lower density of HGMS27 than HGMS41.

Table 3: Cement slurries mixture proportions and classifications

	Cement [kg/m ³]	HGMS41 [kg/m ³]	HGMS27 [kg/m ³]	Water [kg/m ³]	Superplasticizer [kg/m ³]
CS00	1320.2	-	-	580.9	-
CS41	952.5	105.8	-	465.6	2.1
CS27	829.0	-	92.1	405.3	2.8

Figure 2: Particle size distribution for Class G Cement, HGMS27 and HGMS41

Experimental methods

The modified Chapelle test was used to calculate the consumption of CH by HGMS. According to NF P18–513 [15], the amount of consumed CH per gram of HGMS in a solution of 2 g of CaO in 250 ml of water during sixteen hours at 90°C was calculated. The presented results are average values of duplicate measurements for each HGMS.

Hydration of cement slurries with and without the addition of HGMS was traced via heat flow calorimetry using a TAM AIR (TA instrument) isothermal heat conduction calorimeter. In a 10 mL tubular glass ampoule, cement slurries with the proportions established in **Table 3** without plasticizer were mixed. The glass ampoules utilized were provided with a stirring motor that allowed to produce a mechanical mixing of 180 s once the ampoule was closed and set inside the calorimeter with dry cement and HGMS. Both water injection and mechanical mixing occurred inside the calorimeter. Tests were performed in agreement with the standard ASTM C-1679 [16], at 20°C.

A Shimadzu TGA-50 was used for TGA, in which a mass of (9±1 mg) of powdered hydrated cement slurry (sieve No. 200) was heated from room temperature to 800°C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere (30 ml/min). While temperature increased, the sample mass was measured with a precision of 0.01 mg. TGA was carried out in hydrated cement slurries with 7, 28, and 56 days of curing time.

Before testing, millimetre-sized particles of the samples were freeze-dried by direct immersion into liquid nitrogen (-196°C). Subsequently, specimens were freeze-dried at low temperature (-50°C) and pressure (5 Pa) for twenty-four hours as proposed by Zhang and Scherer [17]. Slurries at each curing time were tested from three to five times and the average of the obtained results.

For evaluating the pozzolanic activity in terms of SAI, the American Standard ASTM C 311 [18] was used. This standard proposes a test to evaluate the pozzolanic activity of mineral SCMs, relying on the uniaxial compressive strength (UCS). It compares the strength of plain cement mortars and cement mortars with 20% bwoc replacement by the evaluated SCM. UCS shall be measured after 7 and 28 days of curing. This standard was adapted for well cement slurries, using the proportions mentioned in **Table 3**. Six samples of each slurry at both curing times were tested in an INSTRON 5900 series universal machine provided with a spherical head, at a rate of 0.7 mm/min.

Powder XRD patterns were obtained from a Rigaku D/Max-C Wide Angle Automated X-ray diffractometer equipped with a Cu/K α radiation source (0.154 nm) operating at 40 kV, 30 mA, and room temperature. Diffractograms were recorded in a 2 θ interval of 5°-70° at a step size of 0.02° for Powdered samples (sieve No. 200) of cement slurries after 7 and 28 days of curing.

Finally, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was performed using a FEI QUANTA 250 FEG, operating at 30 KV. Before testing, a thin layer of gold coating was applied on the samples.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Modified Chapelle test

In order to characterize HGMS in terms of their pozzolanic activity, the modified Chapelle test was carried out. Following NF P18 – 513 [15], the modified Chapelle test can be performed to obtain a direct measurement of the pozzolanic activity of SCM by obtaining the amount of CH consumed applying **Equation 1**.

$$CH = 2 \cdot \frac{V_1 - V_2}{V_1} \cdot \frac{74}{56} \cdot 1000 \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where CH: milligrams of consumed CH by a gram of HGMS, V1: HCl (0.1 N) volume required to titrate 25.0+2 ml of filtrate solution of the blanc experiment and V2: HCl (0.1 N) volume required to titrate 25.0+2 ml of filtrate solution of the experiment with HGMS.

Both HGMS were tested, results are shown in **Figure 3**. Given the conditions in which this test is performed, it can be assumed that it evidences the maximum pozzolanic activity potential of HGMS. It can be appreciated that both HGMS show a CH consumption of 1107 mg/g and 1365 mg/g for HGMS41 and HGMS27, respectively. Given that the standard limit established in NF P18 – 513 [15] to consider an

SCM as pozzolan is 700 CH milligrams per SCM gram and that both HGMS overcome it, it is possible to confirm its pozzolanic activity.

Figure 3: CH consumed per gram of HGMS following the modified Chapelle test

Results of this parameter informed by Ali et al. and Vejmelková et al. [19,20] for silica fume and pulverized fly ash are, respectively, 550 and 1600 CH milligrams per SCM gram. Besides, for commercial metakaolin studied by Ferraz et al. [21], values ranging from 900 mg CH/g to 1600 mg CH/g were obtained. Considering these reference results, the HGMS studied in this research show a behaviour similar to that of commercial metakaolin, with a pozzolanic activity (as measured by the modified Chapelle test) lower than that of silica fume.

Ferraz et al. [21] established a correlation between the particle size and the results obtained by this test. The smaller the particle size, the higher the CH consumption per SCM gram. This phenomenon is represented in **Figure 4** for both HGMS, fly ash, silica fume, and commercial metakaolin studied by Ali et al. , Vejmelková et al. [19,20], and Ferraz et al. [21] respectively, in which the tendency mentioned by Ferraz et al. [21] is verified. Furthermore, HGMS presented the same tendency for higher D50. A greater reactivity of HGMS could explain the difference when comparing them with smaller sized fly ash and metakaolins in the cited studies. Therefore, the variation between the CH consumption of HGMS41 and HGMS27 can be explained with their different size.

Figure 4: Modified Chapelle test results for HGMS and reference SCM with varying D50 diameter [19-21]

Isothermal calorimetry test

Cement hydration is the physical-chemical process resulting from mixing water and cement, from which cement hardening occurs. The chemical reactions involved in this procedure are exothermic, generating a heat release. By measuring it, the cement hydration reaction can be monitored. Isothermal calorimetry test was performed for the three cement slurries: the reference one (CS00), the cement slurry with 10% bwoc of HGMS27 (CS27), and the cement slurry with 10% bwoc of HGMS41 (CS41). **Figure 5** shows the heat release curves [mW/g of cement] and the total heat [J/g of cement].

Figure 5: Heat flux normalized per gram of cement obtained following ASTM C 1679 [16]

The heat release curves are characterized by different zones as specified in ASTM C 1679 [16]: the initial thermal power related to the dissolution of cement and the beginning of its hydration, a dormant period, a heat flow increase associated with C3S hydration reactions that contribute to setting and initial strength of cement slurries (related to the second heat flow maximum), a local minimum related to sulphate depletion and the third peak, which is associated with accelerated calcium aluminate activity. The third peak can be challenging to differentiate from the main hydration peak in some mixes containing SCMs [16], which might be the case of slurry CS27. Furthermore, an overlap between this peak and both, the depletion point and the calcium aluminate activity peak, may occur. This is the case of CS27 with HGMS 27, as it can be observed in **Figure 5**, in which only one peak is distinguishable after the dormant period.

As can be appreciated in the close-up view of **Figure 5** and in **Table 4**, the initial thermal power of all three slurries is high when water is mixed with anhydrous cement and HGMS. The heat flow reached a maximum value at 6-8 minutes for all slurries. In accordance to the research developed by Hua et al. [22], CS27 slurry yields the highest heat flow because of HGMS27's relatively high specific surface area (related to its low density and D50). On the other hand, given the lower specific surface area of HGMS41 (related to its higher density and D50), CS41 slurry yields the lowest initial thermal power.

After the initial thermal power, the dormant period occurs. The behaviour of all three slurries is very similar in terms of minimum value of normalized heat flow [mW/g of cement], which is noteworthy since CS27 and CS41 have less cement per unit volume. The slurry with the minimum value is CS27, followed by CS00 and CS41. Nevertheless, this minimum is reached about 30 minutes earlier for CS41 when comparing it to CS00 and CS27, which is an indicator of the acceleration in the hydration produced by HGMS41.

As for the maximums corresponding to the main hydration peaks, the normalized heat flow values are, once more, similar. However, there is a pronounced time variation between CS27 and both CS00 and CS41. CS27 reaches the maximum hydration peak approximately 130 minutes later than CS00 and CS41. As aforementioned, and according to the ASTM C 1679 standard [16], this explains the disappearance of the depletion and calcium aluminate peaks in slurry CS27.

Table 4: Singular points of normalized heat flux and normalized heat of slurries CS00, CS41 and CS27

Value informed	CS00	CS41	CS27
Normalized heat flow local maximum 1 [mW/g cement]	7.19	5.61	7.91
Normalized heat flow local minimum 1 [mW/g cement]	0.38	0.42	0.34
Time for normalized heat flow local minimum 1 [min]	214.1	176.8	218.2
Normalized heat flow local maximum 2 [mW/g cement]	2.38	2.46	2.41
Time for normalized heat flow local maximum 2 [min]	842.8	842.5	972.0
Maximum normalized heat [J/g cement]	316.2	329.3	325.8

Also, the slopes of the curves between the dormant period and the second peak, which can be appreciated in **Figure 5**, show a similar increase rate of the normalized heat flow between CS00 and CS41 slurries. On the other hand, the CS27 slurry shows a slightly lower slope, which means a lower increase rate of the normalized heat flow and, consequently, slower hydration. Finally, the maximum normalized heat release [J/g of cement] is higher for slurries CS41 and CS27 in comparison to CS00, as stated in **Table 4**. These results indicate greater hydration (per gram of cement) within the first 190 hours for slurries with a 10% addition of HGMS27 and HGMS41.

The results found by Ouellet-Plamondon et al. [23] for mortars with the addition of 20% of calcined clay compared to reference mortar showed a significant decrease in the heat flow peaks and the slope of the curve between the dormant period and the second peak. This result is comparable to the behaviour

appreciated in **Figure 5** for CS27. This behaviour changed with the addition of micro limestone and C-S-H seeds. Both admixtures, regardless of the added amount, reduced the dormancy to lower periods than those of reference mortar. The behaviour of micro limestone and C-S-H seeds is similar to that observed in **Figure 5** for HGMS41, which could consequently imply an acceleration in the hydration kinetics with its addition.

Isothermal calorimetry was also used by Cordeiro et al. [24] to study the influence of sugar cane bagasse ash (SCBA) on hydration kinetics. They carried out calorimetry tests on three mixes: a reference mix and two mixes with 10% and 20% bwoc of SCBA. The heat flux results showed a delay in hydration reactions in mixes with SCBA. Even more, the greater its addition, the higher the delay, which was evidenced with a more extensive dormant period. SCBA had a D50 of about 10 μm and still produced a predominant dilution effect. Then, the composition of HGMS is likely to contribute to hydration at an early age. The alkalinity of the cement slurry may enhance the dissolution of HGMS, which releases more sodium into the solution and contributes to more dissolution and enhancement of hydration. Additional experiments in future work should prove this.

In the research of Pane and Hansen [25], silica fume (SF), which has a more similar chemical composition to HGMS than SCBA and limestone, is added to cement pastes. The heat of hydration of plain cement pastes and pastes with 10% in weight of cement replacement by SF are obtained at 23°C with different water to binder ratios (w/b). When using a 0.45 w/b, the heat of hydration obtained for pastes with SF is lower than that obtained for plain cement pastes for the entire measurement period. This is certainly similar to the results of slurry CS27 presented in **Figure 5**. As verified by Pane and Hansen [25] when studying the heat of hydration with 0.35 w/b, this suggests that CS27 may reach higher ultimate heat of hydration than CS00. Therefore, HGMS27 might also be acting as nucleation agents.

From these researches and the obtained results, it can be appreciated that the addition of HGMS of different classes to cement slurries could affect hydration kinetics of cement during the first hours. It is highly probable that depending on physical properties (mainly D50), chemical composition, and percentage of HGMS, these could act as nucleation agents. Given the maximum normalized heat per gram of cement measured, the addition of both HGMS entail, to some extent, an increase in the final heat of hydration.

■ Thermogravimetry analysis

TGA is a widely used technique to measure the amount of CH present in cement pastes since a significant mass loss due to CH dehydration is appreciated. It happens between 440°C and 520°C, and, calculating the mass loss within these temperatures, the amount of CH in the sample can be calculated as expressed in **Equation 2**.

$$CH [\%] = \frac{MM_{CH}}{MM_w} \cdot \frac{M_{440} - M_{520}}{M_i} \cdot 100 \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

where MMCH is the CH molar mass, MMw the water molar mass, M440 the mass of the sample at 440°C, M520 the mass of the sample at 520°C, and Mi the initial mass of the sample.

The amount of CH in cement samples reaches a maximum after a particular curing time and, if there is no carbonation, it remains constant with time. This value varies between 12% and 15% in mass depending on the type of cement analyzed [24-26] and the cement content. Given the reactivity of pozzolanic materials with CH, its addition to cement pastes modifies the mentioned behaviour. The amount of CH reaches a maximum value at a determined curing time (depending on the pozzolanic activity of the SCM), but CH content starts to decrease as it is consumed in the pozzolanic reaction. Therefore, determining the amount of CH of cement pastes at different curing times within this technique can indicate the extent of the pozzolanic reaction of an SCM. Tests were carried out for CS00, CS27, and CS41 slurries at different

curing times (7, 28, and 56 days) to measure the evolution of the amount of CH with curing time. The results are presented in **Figure 6a**.

Furthermore, a parameter called “fixed CH” is defined as the relation between the amount of CH in the reference cement pastes, and the cement pastes with HGMS at a given curing time, taking into account the amount of cement present in the sample (**Equation 3**). This parameter is described by Ghoddousi and Adelzade Saadabadi and by Velázquez et al. [26,27], and it is calculated using **Equation 4**.

$$C = \frac{\text{Cement content [g]}}{\text{Cement content [g]} + \text{HGMS content [g]}} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

$$CH_f^i = \frac{CH_c^i \cdot C - CH_p^i}{CH_c^i \cdot C} \cdot 100 \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

Where CH_f^i is the fixed CH content at a curing time “i” [%], C the cement content in the slurry with HGMS (0.9 in these slurries), CH_c^i the CH content in the reference slurry at curing time “i” [%] and CH_p^i the CH content in the slurry with HGMS at a curing time “i” [%].

When multiplying CH_c^i and C, a quantification of the amount of CH produced by the cement present in slurries with HGMS is obtained. In this product, no effect of the SCMs is considered. The difference between CH_p^i and $(CH_c^i \cdot C)$ is a measurement of the variability in CH content at a curing time “i”, which could only be produced by HGMS. Dividing it by the product of CH_c^i and C, a percentage ratio of the variation of the CH production caused by HGMS and that produced only by cement is determined. Hence, depending on the values of CH_c^i and CH_p^i measured, fixed CH could adopt negative or positive values.

Negative fixed CH values indicate an acceleration in the cement hydration [27], which demonstrate that the SCMs are acting as nucleation agents. This parameter could also adopt positive values, which means that the amount of CH measured by TGA is lower than the expected without considering the effect of the SCM. In their research, Ghoddousi and Adelzade Saadabad and Velázquez et al. established that positive values are indicators of pozzolanic activity [26,27]. For a given cement paste, lower values of CH content obtained through TGA for a cement paste with an SCM mean consumption of CH by the pozzolanic reaction. It is important to notice that at a given curing time both, nucleation and pozzolanic actions can occur to different extents, one showing predominance over the other.

The fixed CH contents for CS27 and CS41 slurries at 7, 28, and 56 days were calculated with **Equation 3** and **Equation 4**. Results obtained for both slurries with HGMS are presented in **Figure 6b**.

After seven days of hydration, fixed CH values are negative for both slurries with HGMS. This indicates that both HGMS are predominantly acting as nucleation agents for cement hydration products. This behaviour is a confirmation of the results obtained from the maximum normalized heat measured within isothermal calorimetry. When increasing the curing time, fixed CH values increase. At curing times of 28 and 56 days, the values obtained for this parameter are positive, indicating the predominance of the pozzolanic activity of HGMS.

Figure 6: (a) CH content at different curing ages obtained from TGA for the three slurries; and (b) Variation in the amount of fixed CH with curing age for slurries with HGMS

Velázquez et al. [27] obtained similar results for some combinations of fly ash and SCMs. These authors obtained negative values of around -20% after 3 and 7 days of curing, and positive values of approximately 15% after 90 days. According to their results and conclusions, it is plausible to state that HGMS are mainly behaving as fly ash, characterized by acting as nucleation agents at low curing times and as pozzolanic materials at high curing times.

Strength activity index

The SAI proposed by ASTM C311 [18] was measured. The evolution of UCS has been used by many authors [28-30]. The compressive strength of cement samples with SCM should increase with increasing curing time. Even more, in accordance with Matos and Sousa-Coutinho [28] and Ismail et al. [30], a significant increase in UCS after 28 days means that pozzolanic activity occurred.

The compressive strength of the three slurries was measured at the different curing times proposed, and results are plotted in **Figure 7a**. Within these results, the SAI were calculated with **Equation 5** and plotted in **Figure 7b**.

$$SAI [\%] = \frac{RC_{a,i}}{RC_{p,i}} \cdot 100 \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

where $RC_{a,i}$ is the UCS [MPa] of cement slurry with HGMS at curing time "i" (7, 28 or 90 days) and $RC_{p,i}$ the UCS [MPa] of the reference cement slurry at curing time "i" (7, 28 or 90 days).

Figure 7: (a) Uniaxial Compressive Strength of cubic specimens for the three slurries; and **(b)** Strength Activity Index obtained from Uniaxial Compressive Strength results

ASTM C-618 [31] establishes the limit for SAI of pozzolans as 75% for a 20% bwoc replacement in cement mortar with a w/c of 0.5. HGMS were added at only 10% bwoc, because of lack of workability for higher proportions, in a cement paste with w/c of 0.44. Despite the composition differences, the SAI limit could be considered a reference value. Both slurries, with seven days of curing, presented an SAI higher than 80%, while at 28 days, this index is higher than 75% only for CS41.

Brooks et al. [32] exposed that the compressive strength does not rely only on the SCM pozzolanic activity but also on other properties such as its particle size and crush strength. The mechanical properties of SCMs also affect the results obtained in this test. They studied the addition of lightweight fillers with low crush strength, such as EPS and expanded thermoplastic spheres, demonstrating how these severely reduce the compressive strength of cement pastes. They compared these results to those obtained for cement pastes with HGMS and fly ash cenospheres, confirming that the shell properties of the SCM and its size affect the mechanical properties. Larger particle size and lower shell thickness decrease the crush strength and, therefore, decrease the compressive strength of cement pastes. Considering these results, the behaviour of the studied slurries could be explained, especially for CS27, since HGMS27 presents lower crush strength than HGMS41 despite its smaller size and therefore has a lower shell thickness.

It also has to be considered that, since HGMS are hollow, its addition also means increasing the unconnected porosity of the slurry, which can be confirmed by the reduction in density of hardened cement slurries with addition of HGMS from 2.19 g/cm³ for CS00 to 1.77 g/cm³ for CS41 and 1.48 g/cm³ for CS27. Furthermore, given the lower density of HGMS27 than HGMS41, 10% bwoc of HGMS27 means a greater volume than HGMS41, which means an even higher volume of unconnected porosity. Thus, it can be concluded that when it comes to UCS, the shell properties of a hollow particle and the volume occupied by the SCM in the cement slurry are more important than its pozzolanic activity. Taking both properties into account, HGMS27 has a higher volume percentage in CS27 than HGMS41 in CS41. Additionally, HGMS27 has a lower crush strength than HMS41. Hence, SAI may not be an appropriate index when calculating the pozzolanic activity of HGMS since there are many variables to consider that are not related to this index.

Powder X-ray diffraction

To appraise the amount of the crystalline phase corresponding to portlandite, powder samples of cement slurries were subjected to the X-ray diffraction test. As indicated in **Figure 8**, six peaks corresponding to the CH crystalline phase can be distinguished in the diffractograms.

Figure 8: X-Ray Diffraction Patterns indicating the most notorious crystalline phases found in the three cement slurries at (a) 7 days of curing time; and (b) 28 days of curing time

The most notorious crystalline phases found in the three cement slurries evaluated are alite, belite, calcite, ferrite and portlandite. In **Figure 9** the areas of the peaks corresponding to the portlandite phase (P) indicate the amount of portlandite phase in each slurry. From 7 to 28 days of curing time, these areas increase for all the slurries showing that the amount of portlandite measured through this test increases with the curing time. Furthermore, the highest increase with curing time corresponds to cement slurry CS00. The increase observed in both cement slurries CS27, and CS41 is similar and considerably smaller. The presence of the HGMS can be linked to portlandite consumption, as showed by the XRD patterns. The differences observed in the variations of the estimated relative amount of portlandite measured through this test between cement slurries with and without HGMS support the development of the pozzolanic activity of both HGMS.

Figure 9: Areas of the peaks corresponding to the portlandite phase for the three slurries at 7 and 28 days of curing time

Scanning Electron Microscopy images

Finally, SEM images obtained for cement slurries CS27 and CS41 at 7 and 28 days of curing time are presented in **Figure 10**. With the aid of EDS analysis, it can be concluded that these images agree with the results obtained in the tests previously discussed. SEM images obtained for cement slurries with 7 days of curing time show the compatibility between cement and HGMS27/HGMS41. A good interface was formed, and as studied and confirmed in the isothermal calorimetry test, both HGMS appear to be acting as nucleation agents for cement hydration products.

Figure 10: Scanning Electron Microscopy images of **(a)** CS27 at 7 days of curing time; **(b)** CS41 at 7 days of curing time; **(c)** CS27 at 28 days of curing time; and **(d)** CS41 at 28 days of curing time

In addition, the interfaces appear to be stronger at 28 days of curing time than at 7 days. This could be an indicator of the interaction between both classes of HGMS and cement paste. As indicated in the modified Chapelle test section, HGMS27 (corresponding to cement slurry CS27) seem to have a more significant interaction with CH than HGMS41 (corresponding to cement slurry CS41).

Evaluation of the pozzolanic activity of hollow glass microspheres

XRD patterns and SEM images obtained on cement slurries at 28 days of curing time confirmed the reactivity of HGMS27 and HGMS41. In addition, SEM images at 7 days of curing time showed the compatibility of these materials with cement developing a good interphase between hydration products and both HGMS.

To reach a general comparison between the performance of HGMS27 and HGMS41, the results obtained are plotted for both HGMS in **Figures 11a** and **11b**. In these figures, the parameters measured and calculated are represented. The closer the value is to the external boundary, the higher the corresponding property for that particular test. These charts allow picturing the performance of both HGMS as nucleation agents and SCMs, respectively.

Figure 11: Performance comparison between each HGMS evaluated with a predominant **(a)** pozzolanic action and **(b)** nucleation action.

Figure 11a presents the main parameters that characterize the nucleation effect of HGMS. To begin with, the absolute fixed CH value at seven days of HGMS41 is larger than that of HGMS27, indicating more activity as a nucleation agent of the former. This result agrees with those obtained in the isothermal calorimetry test. Despite having almost, the same normalized heat and second normalized heat flow

maximum, the time for which the latter is reached is larger for CS27 than for CS41, which means a slower hydration reaction for CS27.

Figure 11b shows the higher pozzolanic activity of HGMS41 than HGMS27 in terms of TGA and SAI. HGMS41 has, on the one hand, a higher density than HGMS27. Since HGMS were added to the slurries at the same proportion, the higher density of HGMS41 entails a smaller volume added to the slurry than HGMS27. On the other hand, HGMS has higher crush strength than HGMS27. This might contribute to a higher compressive strength for CS41 since, as aforementioned, the shell properties of the SCM could severely affect the results obtained in UCS. Given also the higher volume of HGMS27 in CS27 than in CS41, the difference observed in the results obtained in these slurries does represent not only the pozzolanic activity of the HGMS involved but also other properties that unintentionally (but necessarily) affect this test.

Analysing the modified Chapelle test, it can be appreciated that the results obtained followed the relation established in the research of Ferraz et al. [21]: the smaller the D50, the higher the reactivity. Nevertheless, there exists a variation between the results obtained in this test and TGA. According to the former, HGMS27 is the most reactive, while according to the latter, HGMS41 is.

In order to comprehend this difference, special attention must be paid to the conditions in which both tests are performed. On the one hand, the modified Chapelle test is performed by exposing HGMS to a highly concentrated CH solution at high temperatures. The high temperature and the calcium hydroxide availability (which does not change regardless of the class of HGMS being evaluated) within this test provide a set up where the reactivity of the SCM can be tested at its full potential. On the other hand, TGA is performed on cement slurries that were previously cured at room temperature. The CH availability is not the same on every slurry mainly because of the higher volume occupied by HGMS27 than HGMS41, implying a reduction in the cement volume from slurry CS27 to slurry CS41, thus, CH availability. Therefore, the modified Chapelle test evidence the reactivity potential of HGMS, while TGA measures their reactivity under more realistic conditions. These differences in the test conditions could explain why HGMS41 shows to be more reactive when tested using the Chapelle Test than when tested using TGA. Nevertheless, from both tests it is concluded that both HGMS27 and HGMS41 interact with the cement paste with a pozzolanic reaction.

CONCLUSIONS

The pozzolanic reactivity of HGMS was measured within a wide variety of tests. The conclusions obtained from the different tests are the following:

- XRD patterns and SEM images confirmed that HGMS41 and HGMS27 interact with cement. Even more, given the quantification obtained through the modified Chapelle test and thermogravimetric analysis, it can be confirmed that both HGMS present a pozzolanic activity similar to that of smaller sized SCMs, such as metakaolins or fly ash.
- The studied HGMS also present nucleation effect since higher heat flow and heat maximums normalized per gram of cement were obtained for cement slurries with HGMS in the isothermal calorimetry test. For CS41 these values resulted in 3.4% and 4.1% higher than those for CS00 respectively and CS27 resulted in 1.3% and 3.0% respectively. These increases could indicate the formation of additional nucleation sites when adding both HGMS studied to cement slurries, particularly HGMS41.

- Confirming these results, fixed CH measured within TGA at early curing times presented negative values of -1.7 for CS27 to -4.1 for CS41. It can then be concluded that both HGMS act as nucleation agents in the cement hydration reaction, particularly HGMS41.
- Regarding which HGMS is the most reactive, results were inconclusive. The reduction in the CH content and the increase in the fixed CH values measured within TGA for slurries with HGMS at different curing times evidenced pozzolanic activity. CS41 slurry yielded, for 28 and 56 days of curing time, values of fixed CH 57% and 54% higher than CS27 slurry respectively, indicating that HGMS41 is more reactive than HGMS27. CH consumption measured in terms of the modified Chapelle test for both HGMS overcame the standard limit of 700 CH mg per SCM gram, confirming their pozzolanic activity. However, the result obtained for HGMS27 was 23% higher than that of HGMS41, which indicates that HGMS27 are more reactive than HGMS41. Therefore, in the optimum conditions obtained within the modified Chapelle test, HGMS41 presents the higher pozzolanic potential, though, in standard cement paste conditions, HGMS27 has a higher pozzolanic activity.
- The SAI proved to be inconsistent for measuring these hollow SCM's pozzolanic activity since the compressive strength of these materials strongly depends on their physical properties. Both at 7 and 28 days of curing time, a decrease in the compressive strength resulted in slurries CS27 and CS41 in comparison to CS00. The compressive strength of CS41 was higher than on CS27. For CS27, the compressive strength was 13% and 32% lower than for CS00 for 7 and 28 days of curing time respectively. For CS41, the compressive strength was 5% and 11% lower than for CS00 for 7 and 28 days of curing time, respectively. These variations are directly related to the lower crush strength and density of HGMS27 than those of HGMS41.

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